

Implementing NIPUN Bharat Mission in Arunachal Pradesh aligning NEP 2020

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Abstract:

The National Initiative for Proficiency in Reading with Understanding and Numeracy (NIPUN Bharat) Mission was introduced in Arunachal Pradesh by the state government of Arunachal Pradesh in 2021. The mission aims to ensure all children achieve Foundational Literacy and Numeracy (FLN) by the end of Grade III. This study examines the status of implementation of the NIPUN Bharat Mission in Arunachal Pradesh, focusing on number of districts and schools covered, teachers trained and infrastructural facilities provided in the schools. This study conducted a qualitative research approach to analyze the implementation of the Mission in three districts of Arunachal Pradesh: Changlang, Papumpare and Dibang Valley. This study finds that the NIPUN Bharat Mission is implemented across all districts of Arunachal Pradesh with strong institutional support. Ongoing teacher training and digital monitoring have enhanced implementation. Overall, the mission aligns with NEP 2020 and supports improvements in foundational literacy and numeracy.

Keywords: Status of Implementing NIPUN Bharat Mission, Arunachal Pradesh, NEP 2020

1. Introduction

The Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) launched the National Mission on Foundational Literacy and Numeracy (FLN) called National initiative for proficiency in reading with understanding and numeracy (NIPUN Bharat) launched in 5 July 2021 under National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 and centrally sponsored scheme of Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan. **According to NIPUN Bharat Mission guideline (2021)** “the Mission aimed to achieved FLN at an early age, decrease dropout rate from the school, improve the education system and encourage students to learn in a joyful way and become proficiency in reading, writing and calculating by grade III by 2026-27”.

Education is widely recognized as a critical determinant of human development and social transformation. In India, the enactment of the Right to Education Act 2009 and the subsequent framing of the Arunachal Pradesh Right of Children to free and Compulsory Education 2010 marked important steps towards ensuring equitable access to education (**Arunachal audit report, 2011**). In this context pre-primary education in Arunachal Pradesh is provided through Anganwadi centers under the Integrated Child development Services (ICDS) supported through the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) (**Hangsing, 2013**). Now in National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 pre-primary education replace as a foundational stage strengthening Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) and Foundational Literacy and Numeracy (FLN) as the foundation of lifelong learning. In Arunachal Pradesh limited access to digital infrastructure, low digital literacy and geographical challenges further widened foundational literacy and numeracy (FLN) gaps during the pandemic period marked by the researcher, various governmental as well as non-governmental surveys. The Annual Status of Education Report (ASER) 2022 stated that government schools of Arunachal Pradesh enrolment among children age group of 6-14 years declined

steadily from 2006 to 2014 and reached 64.9% in 2014 after which it remained almost the same for the next four years. However, learning levels declined as the share of standard III children who could read a standard II level fell from 18.7% in 2018. The Annual Status of Education Report (ASER) 2023 stated that basic learning levels have remained relatively unchanged over the past decade. However, it also notes that after the prolonged disruption caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, schools have begun to give much needed and focused attention to early grades, which aligns with the objectives of NIPUN Bharat Mission being implemented in all the district of Arunachal Pradesh to strengthen foundational literacy and numeracy in 2021. From the review of literature, it was found that some research studies have been carried out in this area such as: **(Sarkar and Gaur, 2025)** conducted a study on the NIPUN Bharat Scheme focusing on the implementation of foundational literacy and numeracy in three Indian states- Uttar Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Assam; the aimed of study is to evaluate its effectiveness, identify challenges and proposes strategies for improvement. The findings add to discussions on educational equity and offer practical insight for expanding FLN interventions across diverse educational settings in India. **(Chandra, 2024)** explored a study on shaping foundational learning skills. The study analyzed educational data from the 2021-2022 academic year, focusing on enrollment rates, learning outcomes and the impact of intervention on children aged three to eight. The finding shows that India has taken several steps to improve basic education. **(Kanujiya and Jaiswal, 2025)** explored on early childhood care and foundational literacy in NEP 2020 for holistic learning among children aged 3-8 years. It identifies key challenges such as inadequate teacher preparation, infrastructure gaps and uneven implementation across states. The finding shows that despite these issues, effective ECCE programs positively influence literacy, numeracy and socio-emotional development. **(Sthapak, 2025)** examined the impact of foundational literacy and numeracy at the primary level in the context of NEP 2020 and the NIPUN Bharat Mission. The study highlights early success, identifies areas for improving and emphasizes the need to ensure all children achieve essential competencies by the end of Grade 3. **(Tiwari and Kuvad, 2022)** focused on understanding foundational language literacy in context with mission NIPUN Bharat 2021. The study concluded by discussing strategies to improve foundational language literacy and numeracy such as revising the curriculum, using innovative teaching methods, strengthening teacher education, improving assessment practices and providing better administrative support and learning resources. The COVID-19 pandemic widened foundational literacy and numeracy gaps in Arunachal Pradesh due to digital, geographical and infrastructural challenges as reflected in ASER findings. Although NEP 2020 and the NIPUN Bharat Mission aim to address these issues, there is no research study examines on the implementation in Arunachal Pradesh. Therefore, this research paper examines the implementation of NIPUN Bharat Mission in Arunachal Pradesh focusing on number of districts and schools covered, teachers trained and infrastructural facilities provided in the schools.

2. Research Methodology

The present study adopts a Qualitative and Descriptive research method; the population of the present study consists of three districts of Arunachal Pradesh, namely: Changlang, Papumpare and Dibang Valley. The selection of these districts was based on the criterion of having highest number of government primary schools according to the Unified District Information System for Education **(UDISE 21-22)**. For sample Purposive sampling technique was used as they were directly involved in implementing the mission. An Information Scheduled was developed and administered to investigate the status of implementation of NIPUN Bharat Mission in Arunachal Pradesh.

3. Data Analysis and Interpretation

To study the status of Implementation of NIPUN Bharat Mission in Arunachal Pradesh in terms number of districts and school covered, teachers training and infrastructural facilities provided in the schools, a structured Information Scheduled was developed and administered on stakeholder from selected districts. The detail analyses are given below:

1. Numbers of district covered under NIPUN Bharat Mission in the state of Arunachal Pradesh-

As per the responses received from the stakeholders, it was revealed that across all the districts of Arunachal Pradesh are covered under NIPUN Bharat Mission. A total number of 1847 government

primary schools are covered under NIPUN Bharat Mission teachers of the particular schools are trained in phase by manner.

2. Initiatives taken for teachers and headmaster under the NIPUN Bharat Mission-

Headmasters of the schools are given school leadership training and teachers are given subject-specific training twice in a year. The training includes special modules like health and hygiene and moral education etc.

3. Capacity building program for teachers-

Under the mission, teachers are given capacity-building training to strengthen their professional competencies. In July 2025 a four-day FLN training program was conducted, where teachers were engaged in activity-based pedagogical practices to promote an effective classroom teaching-learning environment. The core components covered under capacity building program are: subject specific areas including environmental studies, health and hygiene, moral values and school leadership development for headmasters.

4. Periodic review meeting with districts and stakeholders and its objectives-

Since the beginning the meetings are conducted in online mode, where teachers are required to go through various modules. After completion of each module teachers are provided with test items to assess how much they had learn through module and their performance are evaluated by SSB (State Selection Board), Basically review meetings were conducted every month and were undertaken by the DTF's, BRCC's and CRCC's at district level. The main objective of the review meeting is to examine whether all 21 modules are being used properly. If teachers are unable to complete the assessment they were allowed to reattempt the test, progression to the next test was not permitted until the current test is successfully completed.

5. Key stakeholders involved in these review meetings and follow up action-

The stakeholders involved in these review meetings include Director of SCERT and other SCERT faculty members. The district stakeholders comprises of district administrators, officials from the education department, teachers, parents, school management committee members as well as local MLAs and Panchayat members. Action Plan Development, capacity building, resource allocation and stakeholder engagement are some of the follow-up actions taken by the respective districts.

6. IT based mechanism to facilitate the implementation of the mission-

The DIKSHA FLN portal and NISTHA FLN online training programs served as IT-based mechanisms for capacity building of teachers in foundational learning, covering 21 NCERT-developed modules. In the district of Dibang Valley only 2 (two) schools are facilitated with IT mechanism and remaining schools were provided K-Yan projector.

IT infrastructure is managed and maintained at state by IT Nodal officer, MIS operator and overall responsibility taken by NCERT whereas, Department of Education specifically under the aegis of Samagra shiksha managed all sets of technical and infrastructure is done by SPD office in the respective districts.

7. Workshops and awareness on NIPUN Bharat mission-

Throughout the year several workshops and awareness programs are conducted, Each workshop and awareness program includes a dedicated session on the NIPUN Bharat Mission and it is dived into four quarter:

1st quarter: Launch awareness campaigns through workshop and orientation programs for teachers educators and stakeholders.

2nd quarter: Community Engagement

3rd quarter: Teacher training modules to build capacity and equip educators with FLN focused curriculum.

4th quarter: Evaluation/ Assess through baseline, midline and endline assessment.

8. Follow-up sessions or feedback mechanisms to assess the effectiveness of these workshops-

A Google form is developed and circulated among all teachers to obtain their valuable feedback. In the respective districts a resource person visits each school and document feedback with the aim of gaining an understanding of the existing resources and structural process.

9. Types of activities included in the Vidya Pravesh program and responsible for implementing the Vidya Pravesh program in school-

The Vidya Pravesh Program was also introduced after the COVID-19 pandemic and was conducted at the beginning of the academic session. The activities included ice-breaking sessions especially for student admitted to school for the first time, this program also focused on phonics practice, rhymes and the development of good habits through a play way method (Jaddu Pitara). The teachers, headmasters and school management committee are responsible for implementing the Vidya Pravesh program in school.

10. Teacher trained to implement the Vidya Pravesh program-

Regarding Vidya Pravesh Program teachers are initially trained through online mode. The training was conducted in two phases, where headmasters were trained separately and subject-specific teachers were trained in a different phase. From each school it was mandatory for the headmaster and one teacher to participate in the program. Subsequently the trained headmaster and teacher conducted school-level training for the remaining teaching faculty in their respective schools.

From 2023 onwards face to face training program were introduced. In addition related activities updates were regularly shared through the District Task Force (DTF) WhatsApp groups. These group included school teachers, headmasters, and DIET principals, DDSEs, BEOs and the Director of SCERT from all districts. Through this platform, daily activities conducted in individual schools were updated and monitored.

11. Specific resources designed for play-based learning in teaching learning-

There are several play-based learning materials such as blocks, clay, puzzles, art and craft materials are designed under Jaddu Pitara, which is a box that contains a variety of toy-based teaching learning materials. Some teachers, who are skilled in arts and crafts also design and develop locally made toys based on the specific geographical context of their areas.

12. Teaching learning materials to support the NIPUN Bharat Mission-

To support NIPUN Bharat Mission teaching learning materials, include modules, block, workbooks, maps, toys and puzzles, story cards, flashcards, puppets, alphabet and number charts are provided. In addition, for children aged 3-6 years SCERT provides free educational and support materials including school uniforms school bags, tiffin boxes, geometry boxes, textbooks, comic books, pencils, erasers, sharpeners, umbrellas etc.

13. Digital resources for teaching and learning-

Digital resources for teaching and learning as per responses are DIKSHA platforms are all teaching-learning modules are shared online. In addition, there are five Arunachal DTH channels available for different stages of children such channels are: classes 1-5, classes 6-8, classes 9-10, classes 11-12 and third language. These channels are also available on YouTube enabling equitable access to learning materials for all learners and teachers.

14. Provision for updating the curriculum to keep it relevant to current educational trends-

In alien with NEP 2020 the state of Arunachal Pradesh follows the curriculum developed by NCERT New Delhi.

4. Findings and Discussion

The findings of the study indicate that the NIPUN Bharat Mission has been comprehensively implemented across all districts of Arunachal Pradesh with systematic coverage of government primary schools, structured teacher training and provide teaching materials. Significant emphasis has been placed on capacity building, leadership development and continuous professional support for teachers and headmasters through both online and face to face modes. The use of IT-enabled platforms digital resources and periodic review mechanisms has strengthened monitoring, accountability and instructional practices under the mission. Initiatives such as Vidya Pravesh, play- based learning through Jaddu Pitara and community engagement activities have supported early childhood learning and smooth school transition. Overall, the mission demonstrates a coordinated, inclusive and NEP 2020 aligned approach towards improving foundational literacy and numeracy outcomes in the state.

5. Conclusion

The study concludes that the status of implementing NIPUN Bharat Mission in Arunachal Pradesh has begun with focused efforts on teacher training, teaching materials, infrastructure and foundational literacy and numeracy practices. The state adapted the mission after its national launched by the Government of India and the mission aligns with NEP 2020 and support improvements in Foundational literacy and Numeracy in Arunachal Pradesh.

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